

Synthesis and Antimicrobial Screening of 1,2-Benzisoxazolyl Schiff Bases

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1980, accepted 9 August 1980

SCHIFF bases have gained importance because of the physiological and pharmacological activities associated with them. Schiff bases exhibit anticancer and antitubercular activity^{1,2}. Anticancer Schiff bases have been prepared by the condensation of aniline with substituted benzaldehydes³. Isoxazolyl Schiff bases have been synthesised as possible antibacterial and antifungal agents⁴.

In view of these important observations, some 1,2-benzisoxazolyl Schiff bases have been synthesised to study their antimicrobial activity. All the Schiff bases (I and II in Table 1) were prepared by the

condensation of 7-acetyl-6-hydroxy-3-methyl and 7-acetyl-6-hydroxy-3-ethyl-1,2-benzisoxazoles⁵ with several aromatic amines in presence of catalytic amount of piperidine in alcohol. The structures of these compounds were supported by elemental analyses and infrared spectroscopy.

Antimicrobial activity :

Some of the compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, *S. typhi* and *C. albicans*; but none of the compounds showed significant activity. The antitubercular screening of the compounds was carried out against *Micobacterium tuberculosis* (H₃₇Rv) by a Doub and Youmans' method⁶. Some of the compounds were found to be promising against *M. tuberculosis* (Table 1).

Acknowledgement

Authors are grateful to Dr. M. H. Shah, Asstt. Director, Haffkine Institute, Bombay, for screening the compounds for antimicrobial activity. One of the authors (A.B.D.) is thankful to CSIR, New Delhi, for the award of a Post-doctoral fellowship.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA AND ANTITUBERCULAR ACTIVITY (in $\mu\text{g/ml}$) OF THE SCHIFF BASES (I AND II)

Sl. No.	Substituent R ²	m.p. °C	Yield %
<i>Compound I</i>			
1.	Phenyl	128 ^a	80
2.	2'-Methyl phenyl	155 ^a	82
3.	4'-Methyl phenyl	148 ^b	75
4.	3'-Methoxyphenyl	149 ^b	69
5.	4'-Methoxyphenyl	176 ^b	80
6.	3'-Chlorophenyl	142 ^b	85
7.	4'-Chlorophenyl	166-68 ^b	87
8.	4'-Bromophenyl	170 ^b	83
9.	3'-Hydroxyphenyl	215 ^b	68
10.	4'-Hydroxyphenyl	262 ^b	85
<i>Compound II</i>			
11.	Phenyl	94 ^b	68
12.	2'-Methyl phenyl	142-3 ^b	65
13.	4'-Methyl phenyl	95 ^c	70
14.	2'-Methoxyphenyl	99 ^c	72
15.	3'-Methoxyphenyl	100 ^c	68
16.	4'-Methoxyphenyl	95 ^c	75
17.	3'-Chlorophenyl	83 ^a	71
18.	4'-Chlorophenyl	149 ^b	75
19.	4'-Bromophenyl	166 ^a	72
20.	3'-Hydroxyphenyl	215-16 ^b	80
21.	4'-Hydroxyphenyl	203 ^b	82

All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses

^a=crystallised from methanol,

^b=crystallised from ethanol,

^c=crystallised from 80% ethanol.

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References

1. J. SHN GUPTA, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1964, **29**, 33.
2. L. MUSLIN, W. ROTH and H. H. ERLÉNMYER, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1953, **36**, 886.
3. F. D. POPP, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 1566.
4. K. S. R. KRISHNA MOHAN RAO and N. V. SUBBARAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 1047.
5. K. A. THAKAR and B. M. BHAWAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 875.
6. L. DOUB and G. P. YOUMANS, *Rev. Tuberc.*, 1950, **61**, 407.

Synthesis of 5-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl)-1,3,4-Oxadiazole-2-thione Mannich Bases and Their Biological Evaluations

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Manuscript received 10 April 1980, revised 27 June 1980,
accepted 7 August 1980

OXADIAZOLES have been associated with insecticidal^{1,2}, herbicidal³, antibacterial^{4,5}, hypoglycemic⁶, antitubercular⁷, antiviral⁸, antifungal⁹ and carcinostatic¹⁰ activities. Besides, 5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione yielded Mannich bases with primary aromatic amines¹¹. It was therefore considered worthwhile to synthesise the title products incorporating the 1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione nucleus (Scheme 1) with a view to observe if such compounds could be of biological significance.